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The Land that Time Forgot:
The Coinage of the Kamoeno

by

ANDREW MEADOWS

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The Land that Time Forgot: The Coinage of the Kamoenoi

ANDREW MEADOWS¹

[PLATES 21-22]

In the note that follows I assemble the evidence for a small group of bronze coins from a mint in Asia Minor, whose attribution has so far remained mysterious. I begin with a catalogue of examples known to me, and then discuss the nature of this coinage and its attribution.

Catalogue

Type 1

Obv. Bust of Artemis r., with bow and quiver at shoulder.

Rev. Eagle with wings open standing r. on thunderbolt; above, ΗΝΣ; below, ΑΕ; to l. and r., ΚΑΜΟ-ΗΝΩΝ

O1/R1

- | | | | | |
|----|-------|----|------|---|
| 1. | 7.19g | 0° | 24mm | <i>SNG von Aulock</i> 119. <i>SNG Stancomb</i> 719. Roma E-Sale 74 (2020) 185 |
| 2. | 9.94g | 0° | 25mm | Savoca Blue 24 (2019) 199 |

Type 2

Obv. Laureate head of Zeus right.

Rev. ΚΑΜΟ|ΗΝΩΝ |ΑΕ| ΗΝΣ; all within oak wreath.

O2/R2

- | | | | | |
|----|-------|------|------|---|
| 3. | 5.60g | 330° | 22mm | Berlin 18276370 (1928 Bernhard-Imhoof). Imhoof-Blumer (1908a), pp. 173-5 and (1908b), pp. 285-6, no. 26. ² |
| 4. | 8.24g | | 22mm | Schulten (Köln) 1-3.iv.87, 138. |

O2/R3

- | | | | | |
|----|-------|--|------|----------------------------------|
| 5. | 6.21g | | 22mm | Numismatik Naumann 71 (2018) 135 |
|----|-------|--|------|----------------------------------|

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² The date was read in error by Imhoof-Blumer as ΗΜΣ.

O2/R4

6. 8.10g 0° 24mm Numismatik Naumann 30 (2015) 103

O2/R5

7. 4.62g 0° 24mm *SNG von Aulock* 121. *SNG Stancomb* 720. Roma 19 (2020) 144

O2/R6

8. 5.39g 0° 23mm *SNG von Aulock* 120.

9. 5.05g 330° 23mm Berlin 18276369 (**Pl. 22, A**) (Löbbecke 1906). Löbbecke (1883), p. 83, no. 50

Commentary

The coinage of the Kamoenoi is now known from nine coins and in two types. The first type is represented by two specimens struck from the same die pair. It seems reasonably safe to say that this was a very small production. The second type is now known from seven specimens struck from a single obverse die, used until significant breaks appeared. Again, it seems clear that this was a small coinage. Since the two types were apparently part of the same issue, signed by a single magistrate (**ΑΕ**, **Pl. 22, G**), we can therefore say that the Kamoenoi struck coinage only once, and for a limited purpose. Mean weights and diameters are presented in Table 1, and suggest that no clear attempt was made to differentiate between the two types metrologically. However, both specimens of Type 1 have a distinct yellowish-brass tone to them, whereas all coins of Type 2 have a more green-brown bronze appearance, suggesting that a denominational distinction may have been sought metallurgically. If so, this may have bearing on the question of their place of production.³

	Mean weight	Mean diameter
<i>Type 1</i>	8.57g	24.50mm
<i>Type 2</i>	6.17g	22.85mm
<i>Both Types</i>	6.70g	23.22mm

Table 1. Mean weights and diameters

The identity and the location of the mint of the Kamoenoi have so far eluded identification. Early suggestions were for a mint in Paphlagonia, on the basis of a supposed similarity of Type 2 to a coin of Pompeiopolis in that region,⁴ and Pontos, where they are placed in the two *Sylloges* in which specimens of Types 1 and 2 have been published. However, as Louis Robert repeatedly stressed, there is precisely

³ For analysis of the use of brass (*aurichalcum*) in Asia Minor from the later 1st century BC to the Flavian period see Cowell *et al.* 2000, noting (pp. 673–4) a significant concentration in the region of Phrygia, where there are sources of zinc: ‘there is a relationship between the distribution of brass coinage and the occurrence of zinc which implies long-standing local brass industries in the region starting before the Roman period.’

⁴ See Löbbecke 1883, p. 83 n.1.

no basis for this attribution,⁵ and his agnosticism has been followed in more recent scholarship.⁶

The name of the Kamoenoi is wholly unattested in ancient literature, administrative documents and the epigraphic record. The name does not sound especially Greek and it may be that we have here the conversion of an originally Luwian toponym into an ethnic, as seems to be the case for some other places that identified themselves as *katoikiiai*, and the names of which take similarly odd forms.⁷ A recent collection of the evidence for toponyms ending in -ηνος lists just four examples for Pontos and Paphlagonia, seven for Bithynia and Troas, ten in the Troad and Aeolis, nine in Lydia, three in Caria and nineteen in Phrygia and Pisidia.⁸

Only the coins attest to the existence of the Kamoenoi, and they alone can suggest a time, place and occasion of production. Without a single provenance for any of the known specimens, we are left with two elements on which to concentrate: their design and their legends. The obverses provide us with little help, bearing standard depictions of Zeus and Artemis. However, the quality of engraving is good, suggesting a mint with access to craftsmen capable of a high standard of work. Since the Kamoenoi produced no other coinage, they must have turned to a centre of more regular production. At first sight, the reverses are even less helpful. The Kamoenoi could not, it seems, conjure up a suitable image for the reverse of one type, satisfying themselves for Type 2 simply with the legends surrounded by an oak wreath.

Prima facie, therefore, Type 1 offers more scope for attribution. The type of an eagle with its wings open, at the point either of landing or taking off, is not especially common. One obvious coinage with which to compare this is the Mithridatic bronze city-coinage of similar type, struck at Amaseia, Amisos, Komana, Gazioura, Laodikeia, Kabeira, Pharnakeia Taulara, Abonouteichos, Amastris, Pimolisa and Sinope in Pontos and Paphlagonia.⁹ However, the style of engraving is generally coarser on the Mithridatic issues, there is no obvious metrological resemblance between either of the two Mithridatic denominations and our coins, and the eagle on the former is depicted with its wings half-open, rather than fully spread as on the reverse of the Kamoenoi. In this respect, a much closer comparison can be made with the substantial first century coinage of Phrygian Apameia, which on its largest denomination has a reverse depicting an eagle with outstretched wings alighting on

⁵ Robert & Robert 1954, pp. 335–6, n.6 and 1962, pp. 369–70. And note *ibid.*, p. 17 n.1, where he also rules out identification with Kamai in Lydia. On the location of the last in the region of Apollonis, on the basis of coin provenance and epigraphical evidence on the one hand and die-sharing in the imperial period on the other, see Robert 1982, pp. 316–7 and 1980, p. 187 n. 57.

⁶ See, for example, Zgusta 1984, p. 218, no. 421–2; Olshausen, & Biller 1984, p. 106 (‘Dazu besteht kein begründeter Anlass’) and Leschhorn 1993, pp. 39–40.

⁷ Note, for example, οἱ κατοικοῦντες... Κολοηνοί and [ἡ κα]τουκία ἢ Κορακη[νῶν from Lydia (Malay 1994, nos. 51 and 38, with discussion of names at pp. 36–7). In Phrygia, for example, we find ὁ δῆμος Σοηνῶ[ν] (*MAMA* 10.69), ὁ δῆμος Ὀ[τροηνῶ]ν (Ramsay 1895–7, p. 703, no. 539; cf. *RPC* IV [temporary] 1855–7; Otrous claimed foundation by Alexander the Great: Ramsay, 1895–7, p. 702, no. 638) and Καδοηνῶν (e.g. *RPC* I. 3062–8).

⁸ See Dale 2015 for the Luwian nature of these names and regional lists.

⁹ Imhoof-Blumer 1912, Type III; Olshausen *et al.* 2009, pp. 173–7, Type Xa (19.59g, 28mm) and Xb (7.15g, 19mm).

or leaving an oblong Maeander-patterned block.¹⁰ The design and its execution are much closer to the Kamoenoi Type 1 (compare **Pls 21, 1-2** and **22B**), and there does seem to be a broad metrological similarity with the Apameian coins which ‘range from 4.4 to 12.26g with a cluster around 7.0–10g, and have diameters mostly in the 21–24mm range’.¹¹ Moreover, there is clear evidence that the coinage of Apameia, which was issued in massive quantities, served as a typological model for a number of other coinages, including Antioch in Pisidia, Acmonia in Phrygia and Tavium in Galatia (**Pl. 22, C, D, E**).¹²

However, if we turn back to the reverse of Type 2, it is not quite such sterile ground as it might at first seem. While it is very familiar from the imperial period, the use of a full ethnic within wreath as a reverse design on bronze coinage of the Hellenistic period is, in fact, comparatively rare in Asia Minor. And when it comes to the combination of a full ethnic plus a magistrate in monogrammatic form within a wreath, there is only one other example known to me. Produced between c. 88 and 40 BC, and so closely contemporary with our coinage (see below), this is from Eumeneia and, also like our coinage, features a head of Zeus on the obverse (**Pl. 22, F**).¹³ Like the coinage of nearby Apameia, Eumeneian bronze was issued in substantial quantities, and circulated regionally, not just in its home city.¹⁴ That the two closest parallels for the reverse types of the coinage of the Kamoenoi are from towns in Phrygia just 50 km apart, surely has geographical implications for where we search for our elusive mint.¹⁵

The other element that might help us towards an attribution comes in the legend. On both issues there is a date, ΗΝΣ (Year 268). There are very few eras on which a year 268 could fall within the 1st century BC, when these coins seem stylistically to fall. The possibilities have been thoroughly discussed by Leschhorn,¹⁶ and his conclusions may be summarised as follows:

¹⁰ Ashton 2016, Type 1.

¹¹ Ashton 2016, p. 380.

¹² CNG EA 406 (2017) 424 (Apameia). Savoca Blue 101 (2021), 280 (Pisidian Antioch); Savoca Silver 33 (2019) 170 (Acmonia); *SNG von Aulock* 6237 (Tavium). The evidence is collected by Imhoof-Blumer 1908b, p. 143 and Ashton 2016, pp. 385–6. In terms of posture, one should also note the similarity to the later bronze types of Pergamum in the name of Athena Nikephoros, which have an owl instead of an eagle: Westermarck 1995, series 2; for a date for these between c. 80 and 10 BC see Chameroy 2012, no. 37 with pp. 153–4 on the chronology. Rare silver hemidrachms on the cistophoric standard also exist with the same types: Westermarck 1997, p. 30 n.12. Like the Apameian coins, these too were apparently imitated, at Adramyion: von Fritze 1913, nos. 42–9.

¹³ Rauch summer 2011, 323

¹⁴ The coinage has been studied by Ünal 2014, who reports 58 obverse dies from 217 specimens. Significant numbers are reported in the Museums at Denizli, Üpak and Afyon (p. 625). For the circulation of Apameian bronze, see Ashton 2016, pp. 385–7, noting a broad pattern of evidence across central Anatolia, and even beyond.

¹⁵ On the relationship between Seleucid Apameia and Attalid Eumeneia see Thonemann 2011, esp. pp. 150–1 on the Roman road between the two towns.

¹⁶ Leschhorn 1993, pp. 39–40.

Era	Start date	Year 268
<i>Bithynian/Pontic royal</i>	297/6 BC	40/39 BC
<i>Bithynian civic</i>	282/1 BC	15/14 BC
<i>Seleucid</i>	312/1 BC	55/4 BC

Table 2. Summary of Leschhorn 1993.

The Bithynian civic era is probably too late, since it would require our coinage to be of Augustan date. The Bithynian/Pontic era is theoretically feasible but, as Leschhorn notes, the continuation of its use after the end of both kingdoms seems unlikely. Moreover, with the supposed Pontic location of the mint disposed of, there is no particular reason to assume it. And, as we have seen, there are typological grounds for preferring a mint location further south.

This leaves the Seleucid era as the only possible candidate, and this identification is confirmed by the fact that the figures are written in reverse order, as they always are for this era.¹⁷ Our question then becomes, who could still have been using the Seleucid Era in the mid 50s BC? A survey of the use of the era in Asia Minor after the removal of Seleucid control north of the Taurus produces a thin result.¹⁸ Indeed, once the supposed use of the era at Alexandria Troas is removed from consideration,¹⁹ the only examples identified by Leschhorn outside of the Bithynian and Pontic regions are from the 2nd century AD. Our coinage is a remarkable outlier, clearly not to be interpreted as part of broader phenomenon. Rather, it seems most probably to be regarded as a tenacious survival of Seleucid dating in a place that, one might say, time forgot. If we look instead at a map of places where the era is attested in use during Seleucid rule, this is perhaps the footprint within which our mysterious coinage belongs. Of course, our evidence for the use of the Seleucid era is at the mercy of accidents of survival and it may help to add to this map a layer of firmly attested Seleucid colonial activity, which extends the range a little. But if we then overlay the instances of places which the Apameian coin type can be seen to have influenced, there emerges a small and distinct pocket of Seleucid territory, where colonisation and use of the calendar are both attested, along with imitation of Apameia (Figures 1 and 2).

Remote though this region was one from the Seleucid heartlands, its proximity to the main east-west route through southern Asia Minor, and especially to the great emporium of Apameia-Kelainai in fact ensured its tight integration into the Seleucid state. The Seleucid era is in evidence in the marking out of the territory of Synnada, presumably as part of the settlement of colonists (*MAMA* 4. 75).²⁰ With the exception of the curious issues of Tavium, all of the potential models for the types of the coinage of the Kamoenoi fall within this zone.

¹⁷ See Kosmin 2018, pp. 46–8.

¹⁸ See the tabulation by Leschhorn 1993, pp. 437–8.

¹⁹ For the case against this see Ellis-Evans 2016, p. 127.

²⁰ Further to the southeast, in another community whose ancient name has not survived, the first known copy of the famous edict of Antiochus III of 194/3 was found by Maurice Holleaux at Dodurgalar: Ma 1999, pp. 354–6, no. 37.

Fig. 1. Map showing Seleucid colonies (diamonds), dates (grey circles), and imitator/imitations (stars).

Fig. 2. Map showing detail of the area of Apameian imitation.

As to the purpose of this coinage, we are in the dark. The imitation of local types, if they have been correctly identified, suggests a small community briefly joining the bigger communities of the region, but without the self-confidence or strength of identity to assert anything more than the generic in their coin designs. These, are not, for example, self-evidently *panegyris* coinages.²¹

The choice of Seleucid era, on the other hand, is striking. That it should re-emerge in this way under Roman rule is not, perhaps in itself surprising. In Syria, for example, ‘there seems to be no evidence that the Romans ever intervened in these matters’, and the Seleucid era continues to appear sporadically.²² More surprising is the fact that the use of the Seleucid era survives in an area that had previously been under Attalid rule, which had brought with it the use of Attalid regnal dating in a number of places. We must assume that the community of the Kamoenoi had resisted the urge (or necessity) to integrate themselves within the Attalid state that was felt, for example, by the ‘Macedonians’ at Doidye and Kobedyle in Lydia.²³ And, of course, the decision to place any sort of date on a coinage was not automatic. Few other communities chose to do this, and the Kamoenoi perhaps were making a point about their pedigree in so conspicuously choosing to place an era, and this era in particular, on their coins.

The precise circumstances that lay behind the singular decision of the Kamoenoi to strike coin are lost. The reasons may have been purely local and ephemeral. But it is perhaps worth noting that in 56 BC, the year before our issues seem to have been struck, the three Phrygian dioceses of Laodiceia-Kibyra, Apameia and Synnada, which essentially cover the area identified in Fig. 2, had been detached from *Provincia Asia* and added to *Cilicia*. As a result, the two cistophoric mints of Laodiceia and Apameia moved under the control of the governor of Cilicia, P. Lentulus Spinther.²⁴ The effect of this administrative shift at Apameia was dramatic. As Metcalf has pointed out,²⁵ the mint saw a marked increase in output under Spinther. His coinage consumed 15 dies, three times higher than next highest pro-magistrate’s coinage (Fig. 3). Even allowing for his longer tenure of the post (Fig. 4), we can see that Spinther put significantly more silver into circulation at Apameia, and to a lesser extent at Laodiceia, than any other Roman governor of the region. It may be that we should see the coinage of the Kamoenoi as an epichoric reaction to this sudden flood of silver, albeit the mechanics of this reaction are not clearly understandable.

²¹ For a recent survey of the phenomenon see Psoma 2008 and Thonemann 2011, pp. 117–21.

²² See Kushnir-Stein 2005, quotation from p. 160. In *Cilicia*(?), Thonemann draws my attention to the intriguing newly emerged silver issues bearing the clearly Seleucid date ΘΚΣ (229) = 84/3 BC: see e.g. Leu 2 (2018) 125.

²³ *OGIS* 314–*TAM* v.2.1188 and *TAM* v.1.221. Both colonies are assumed by Cohen to have begun as Seleucid settlements: Cohen 1995, pp. 206–7, 214.

²⁴ Stumpf 1991, pp. 46–50.

²⁵ Metcalf 2017, p. 5.

Fig. 3. Output (dies) of the proconsular governors at Laodiceia and Apameia.

Fig. 4. Output (dies *per annum*) of the proconsular governors at Laodiceia and Apameia.

Whatever the catalyst for this late flowering of coinage among the Kamoenoi, there would not be another season. As we do not know their origins, so we are ignorant of the subsequent fate of this community. They never minted again, which is perhaps a sign that they were absorbed into a larger community as Roman rule was consolidated.²⁶

²⁶Peter Thonemann points out to me the case of Sebaste, mid-way between Eumeneia and Akmoneia, which was created by the synoecism of a number of villages in the reign of Augustus, and began to strike coinage almost immediately: see *MAMA* xi, pp. xvi–xvii for the epigraphic evidence and *RPC* I 3153–4 for the Augustan coinage.

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Type 1

1

2

Type 2

3

4

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6

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PLATE 22

A. Löbbecke (1883), p. 83, no. 50

B. Apameia. CNG EA 406, 424

C. Antioch in Pisidia. Savoca Blue 101 (2021) 280

D. Akmonia. Savoca Silver 33 (2019) 170

E. Tavium, *SNG von Aulock* 6237

F. Eumeneia. Rauch summer 2011, 323

G. Monogram (Coin 5)

